

Consistency, Reliability, and Validation of the 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Mexican Patients with Depressive Disorders and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

José Carlos Medina-Rodríguez¹

Resumen

■ INTRODUCCIÓN

Los trastornos depresivos (TD) incluyen una variedad de condiciones psiquiátricas que afectan el funcionamiento diario y la calidad de vida. Estos tienen una alta prevalencia a nivel mundial, especialmente entre personas con enfermedades concomitantes como la diabetes mellitus tipo 2 (DMT2). La relación bidireccional entre los TD y la DMT2 a menudo conduce a la falta de adherencia al tratamiento, lo que agrava las complicaciones. La **Escala de Adherencia a Medicación de Morisky** (MMAS-8) es una herramienta utilizada para evaluar la adherencia, pero sus propiedades psicométricas requieren validación en México.

Objetivo: Describir las características sociodemográficas y clínicas de mexicanos adultos con DMT2 y TD, así como evaluar la consistencia interna, la confiabilidad interevaluador y la validez de constructo de la versión en español de la MMAS-8 mediante análisis factoriales exploratorios y confirmatorios.

Materiales y Métodos: Se realizó un estudio transversal en el Hospital Ángeles del Pedregal en la Ciudad de México, entre julio de 2021 y enero de 2022. El estudio incluyó participantes ambulatorios mayores de 18 años en tratamiento para DMT2.

Resultados: Entre 140 participantes (58.6% hombres, 41.4% mujeres; edad promedio 61.07 años), el trastorno depresivo mayor fue el TD más prevalente (41.4%). La MMAS-8 demostró una fuerte consistencia interna ($\alpha = 0.88$) e

AFFILIATIONS

- 1.- Unidad de Fomento a la Investigación, Instituto Nacional de Psiquiatría Ramón de la Fuente Muñiz, Ciudad de México, México;
- 2.- Dirección de Enseñanza, Instituto Nacional de Ciencias Médicas y Nutrición Salvador Zubirán, México City, México.

CORRESPONDENCE

José Carlos Medina-Rodríguez.
Unidad de Fomento a la Investigación,
Instituto Nacional de Psiquiatría,
Ramón de la Fuente Muñiz, Calzada
México-Xochimilco No. 101,
Tlalpan, México City, México.
Phone: +525544438609. E-mail:
revistaapm@psiquiatriasapm.org.mx

Received: October 10, 2024

Approved: October 31, 2024

Consistency, Reliability, and Validation of the 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Mexican Patients with Depressive Disorders and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

identificó tres factores distintos relacionados con la adherencia mediante un análisis factorial exploratorio y confirmatorio. Se obtuvo una alta confiabilidad interevaluador ($\kappa = 0.88$ para la MMAS-8; $\kappa = 0.82$ para la HDRS). Se encontró una asociación significativa entre mayor gravedad de los TD y menor adherencia ($\chi^2 = 27.32, p < 0.001$). Conclusiones: La MMAS-8 es una herramienta consistente, confiable y válida para evaluar la adherencia a la medicación entre mexicanos con TD y DMT2. La asociación entre la gravedad de los TD y la baja adherencia resalta la importancia de la atención integral para la salud mental y metabólica.

Palabras Clave: *Escala de Adherencia a Medicación de Morisky, Adherencia a Medicación, Trastornos Depresivos, Diabetes Mellitus Tipo 2, Validación Psicométrica, Atención Integral.*

■ ABSTRACT

Background: Depressive disorders (DD) encompass a variety of psychiatric conditions that affect daily functioning and quality of life. These disorders have a high global prevalence, especially among individuals with comorbidities such as Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). The bidirectional relationship between DD and T2DM often leads to treatment non-adherence, exacerbating complications. The Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8) is a tool used to assess adherence, but its psychometric properties require validation in Mexico.

Objective: To describe the sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of adult Mexicans with T2DM and DD, as well as to evaluate the internal consistency, inter-rater reliability, and construct validity of the Spanish version of the MMAS-8 using exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted at Hospital Ángeles del Pedregal in Mexico City, between July 2021 and January 2022. The study included ambulatory participants aged 18 and older undergoing treatment for T2DM.

Results: Among 140 participants (58.6% male, 41.4% female; average age 61.07 years), Major Depressive Disorder was the most prevalent DD (41.4%). The MMAS-8 demonstrated strong internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.88$) and identified three distinct adherence-related factors through exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses. High inter-rater reliability was observed ($\kappa = 0.88$ for the MMAS-8; $\kappa = 0.82$ for the HDRS). A significant association was found between greater DD severity and lower adherence ($\chi^2 = 27.32, p < 0.001$).

Conclusions: The MMAS-8 is a consistent, reliable, and valid tool for assessing medication adherence among Mexicans with DD and T2DM. The association between DD severity and low adherence highlights the importance of integrated care for mental and metabolic health.

Keywords: *Morisky Medication Adherence Scale, Medication Adherence, Depressive Disorders, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Psychometric Validation, Integrated Care.*

■ BACKGROUND

Depressive Disorders (DD)

DD are a group of affective, cognitive, and behavioral diagnoses that disrupt an individual's overall functioning (Otte et al., 2016). Symptoms include persistent sadness, irritability, emptiness, anhedonia (loss of interest or pleasure in most activities),

Consistency, Reliability, and Validation of the 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Mexican Patients with Depressive Disorders and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

changes in appetite or weight, sleep disturbances (insomnia or hypersomnia), psychomotor agitation or retardation, fatigue, low energy, feelings of worthlessness or excessive guilt, difficulty concentrating, and recurrent thoughts of death or suicidal ideation (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). When these symptoms persist and intensify, they lead to the development of a specific DD (Otte et al., 2016).

According to the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition* (DSM-5), depressive disorders include major depressive disorder, persistent depressive disorder (formerly known as dysthymia), and other specified or unspecified conditions (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). These disorders are characterized by their chronicity, severity, and significant impact on the individual's quality of life (Proudman et al., 2021). Epidemiological data show that the prevalence of DD varies across populations, with higher rates observed in women, individuals with chronic medical conditions, and those facing psychosocial stressors (Gutiérrez-Rojas et al., 2020).

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM)

T2DM is a chronic metabolic disorder marked by insulin resistance and a relative deficiency in insulin secretion, leading to hyperglycemia (Ahmad et al., 2022). The pathophysiology of T2DM is multifactorial, involving genetic, environmental, and lifestyle influences such as obesity, physical inactivity, and unhealthy dietary patterns (Galicia-García et al., 2020).

Diagnosis is based on criteria established by the American Diabetes Association, including fasting plasma glucose levels ≥ 126 mg/dL, 2-hour plasma glucose levels ≥ 200 mg/dL during an oral glu-

cose tolerance test, hemoglobin A1c $\geq 6.5\%$, or a random plasma glucose level ≥ 200 mg/dL in the presence of classic hyperglycemic symptoms like polyuria, polydipsia, and unexplained weight loss (American Diabetes Association Professional Practice Committee, 2022). T2DM has become a global public health challenge, with its prevalence rapidly increasing worldwide (Khan et al., 2020). The condition is associated with numerous complications, including cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, nephropathy, retinopathy, and increased susceptibility to infections (Cannon et al., 2018).

Therapeutic Adherence

Therapeutic adherence refers to the degree to which a patient's behavior—such as taking medication, following a prescribed diet, and making lifestyle changes—aligns with the recommendations provided by a healthcare professional (Horwitz & Horwitz, 1993). Adherence is a critical factor in the success of treatment, especially in chronic conditions like Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), where long-term management is essential for preventing complications and improving outcomes (Krass et al., 2015).

Depressive Disorders and their Association with T2DM

A growing body of evidence highlights a bidirectional relationship between DD and T2DM (Roy & Lloyd, 2012). Individuals with DD have an elevated risk of developing T2DM, and conversely, the risk of developing DD is significantly higher in patients with T2DM, with estimates suggesting a two- to three-fold increase in prevalence compared to the general population (Holt et al., 2014). Furthermore, depressive symptoms in patients with T2DM are linked to poorer glycemic control,

Consistency, Reliability, and Validation of the 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Mexican Patients with Depressive Disorders and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

leading to an elevated risk of diabetes-related complications (Świątoniowska-Lonc et al., 2021).

Justification

Given the established link between DD and T2DM, it is essential to have consistent, reliable, and valid tools for assessing therapeutic adherence, particularly in diverse populations. The 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8) is commonly used in clinical practice and research to evaluate adherence. However, its psychometric properties—including internal consistency, inter-rater reliability, and construct validity—must be measured across different cultural contexts to ensure its effectiveness. In Mexico, where the prevalence of both DD and T2DM is high, it is especially important to assess the psychometric properties of this scale within the Mexican population (Martinez-Perez et al., 2021).

Objectives

To: **a)** Describe the sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of Spanish-speaking Mexican adults diagnosed with T2DM and DD; **b)** assess the internal consistency, inter-rater reliability, and construct validity of the Spanish version of the MMAS-8 through exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses; and **c)** explore the associations between the results of both scales.

■ MATERIALS AND METHODS

Design and Setting

This cross-sectional study was conducted at *Hospital Ángeles del Pedregal* (HAP) in Mexico City between July 2021 and January 2022.

Sample

The study sample included outpatients aged 18 years and older receiving treatment for T2DM at HAP. Given that the MMAS-8 consists of eight items, a minimum sample size of 80 participants was initially set. However, to enhance statistical power, additional participants were recruited. Enrollment was conducted using an open, convenience, and consecutive sampling method, without randomization (Zongo et al., 2016).

Selection Criteria

Inclusion criteria consisted of outpatients with a known or recently diagnosed case of T2DM, as defined by the American Diabetes Association guidelines (*American Diabetes Association Professional Practice Committee, 2022*). Exclusion criteria included any chronic or acute medical conditions that could interfere with the study procedures.

■ MEASUREMENT INSTRUMENTS

Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders - Fifth Edition (DSM-5)

The DSM-5 is a comprehensive manual for diagnosing mental health conditions, including DD. It classifies DD based on specific criteria used by clinicians to assess and diagnose these conditions. For a diagnosis of DD, symptoms must cause distress or impairment in social, occupational, or other domains of functioning and must not be due to the physiological effects of a substance or another medical condition (*American Psychiatric Association, 2013*).

Consistency, Reliability, and Validation of the 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Mexican Patients with Depressive Disorders and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS)

The HDRS is one of the most widely recognized tools for assessing the severity of depressive symptoms in individuals diagnosed with DD. The original HDRS consists of 17 items, with psychometric properties validated across multiple countries, including Spanish-speaking populations (Hamilton, 1960; Trajković et al., 2011).

Morisky Medication Adherence Scale - 8 Items Version (MMAS-8)

The MMAS-8 is a validated tool for assessing patients' adherence to prescribed therapeutic regimens. It evaluates intentional and unintentional non-adherence and has been psychometrically validated in Spanish (Moon et al., 2017; Martínez-Perez et al., 2021).

Procedure

The study was initially submitted for review and approval by the Institutional Review Board of the HAP. Participants were recruited through a combination of advertisements, referrals from healthcare providers, and direct invitations during clinical visits. The diagnosis of T2DM was confirmed by a certified internist, after which participants were screened for DD by a board-certified psychiatrist who also administered the HDRS to assess depressive symptoms. The MMAS-8 was then administered by the principal investigator (A) and the secondary investigator (B). Sociodemographic and clinical data were collected using a document specifically designed for this study. Data from the HDRS and MMAS-8 assessments were directly entered into a database for subsequent analysis. Each participant's evaluation lasted approximately 90 minutes,

with breaks provided as needed to ensure comfort and minimize fatigue.

Ethical Aspects

This study adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki, with informed consent obtained from all participants. The Ethics Committee of HAP reviewed and approved the study (Certification No. HAP-2608).

Statistical Analysis

Measures of central tendency and dispersion were calculated for quantitative variables, and frequencies were obtained for categorical variables. Internal consistency was assessed by calculating Cronbach's alpha (α) for the total sample. Construct validity was examined through exploratory factor analysis with Varimax rotation. Items from the MMAS-8 that did not have factor loadings of 0.30 or higher in the exploratory analysis were excluded for confirmatory factor analysis to ensure the integrity and conceptual relevance of the MMAS-8. The confirmatory factor analysis used R-squared values to evaluate model fit, providing an accessible measure of how well the factors explained variance in the MMAS-8 items. Inter-rater reliability was assessed using Cohen's Kappa (κ) for the total scores of the MMAS-8 and the HDRS. Additionally, a chi-square test (χ^2) was performed to examine the association between medication adherence with the MMAS-8 (categorized as 'Low' versus 'Not Low') and DD severity with the HDRS (categorized as 'Mild' vs. 'Moderate-Severe'), with a p-value of < 0.05 considered statistically significant. Statistical analyses were performed using R-Studio (R Core Team, 2023).

Consistency, Reliability, and Validation of the 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Mexican Patients with Depressive Disorders and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

■ RESULTS

Sociodemographic and Clinical Characteristics

The study included 140 participants, with $n = 82$ identifying as male (58.6%) and $n = 58$ as female (41.4%). The average age of the participants was 61.07 ± 13.46 years, ranging from 38 to 87 years. Regarding physical activity, $n = 40$ participants (28.6%) reported engaging in regular physical activity, while $n = 100$ (71.4%) did not. In terms of diabetic therapy, $n = 42$ participants (30%) were on oral antidiabetic monotherapy, $n = 12$ (8.6%) on insulin monotherapy, and $n = 36$ (25.7%) were using combination therapy. Additionally, $n = 38$ participants (27.1%) adhered to a diet adjusted for T2DM, while the majority ($n = 84$, 60%) did not.

The most prevalent DD identified was major depressive disorder ($n = 58$, 41.4%), followed by recurrent major depressive disorder ($n = 49$, 35%) and persistent depressive disorder ($n = 33$, 23.6%). Depressive symptoms were assessed using the HDRS, with an average score of 13.33 ± 6.52 , indicating mild to moderate symptoms. Among the participants, $n = 49$ (35%) scored in the 'Normal' range (scores ≤ 7), $n = 58$ (41.4%) in the 'Mild' range (scores 8–17), $n = 21$ (15%) in the 'Moderate' range (scores 18–24), and $n = 12$ (8.6%) in the 'Severe' range (scores ≥ 25).

Internal Consistency

The internal consistency of the MMAS-8, demonstrated by Cronbach's alpha of $\alpha = 0.88$, which confirms the reliability of the scale as a measure of medication adherence in this sample.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Exploratory factor analysis of the MMAS-8 items identified three distinct factors, as shown in **Table 1**.

Consistency, Reliability, and Validation of the 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Mexican Patients with Depressive Disorders and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

Table 1: Exploratory Factor Analysis Factor Loadings of the MMAS-8.

MMAS-8 Items	Factor 1 Low-Medium Adherence	Factor 2 High Adherence	Factor 3 Specific Adherence Behaviors
Item 1	-0.68	0.60	-0.01*
Item 2	0.97	-0.26	-0.01*
Item 3	-0.86	-0.51	-0.01*
Item 4	-0.04	1.00	0.02*
Item 5	-0.01*	-0.11	0.09
Item 6	0.09*	-0.01	-0.08
Item 7	-0.06	-0.04*	-0.27
Item 8	-0.01	0.07*	0.55
Eigenvalue	2.34	1.64	1.18
Variance (%)	29.10%	20.39%	14.59%

Note: Loadings marked with an asterisk () indicate non-significant factor loadings that were retained due to the inverse relationship between DD and medication adherence as measured by the MMAS-8.*

Consistency, Reliability, and Validation of the 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Mexican Patients with Depressive Disorders and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

A confirmatory factor analysis was conducted to validate the factor structure identified in the exploratory analysis, shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis R-Squared Values of the MMAS-8.

MMAS-8 Items	Factor 1 Low-Medium Adherence	Factor 2 High Adherence	Factor 3 Specific Adherence Behaviors
Item 1	0.46	0.36	0.01
Item 2	0.93	0.07	0.01
Item 3	0.74	0.26	0.01
Item 4	0.01	0.99	0.02
Item 5	0.01	0.01	0.09
Item 6	0-01	0.01	0.07
Item 7	0.01	0.01	0.07
Item 8	0.01	0-01	0.55

Note: R-squared values indicate the proportion of variance in each item explained by its corresponding factor.

Consistency, Reliability, and Validation of the 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Mexican Patients with Depressive Disorders and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

Inter-Rater Reliability

The inter-rater reliability analysis showed Kappa coefficients of $\kappa = 0.88$ for the MMAS-8 and $\kappa = 0.82$ for the HDRS.

Association between Depressive Disorders and Medication Adherence

A χ^2 test was conducted to assess the association with medication adherence, revealing $\chi^2 = 27.32$, $p < 0.001$.

Discussion

The most significant finding of this study is that the MMAS-8 demonstrated strong internal consistency, inter-rater reliability, and construct validity in this sample of Spanish-speaking Mexican participants with DD and T2DM.

Regarding sociodemographic and clinical data, the study had a nearly equal distribution of males and females, with major depressive disorder being the most prevalent DD, aligning with findings from Medina-Mora et al. (2007), a major epidemiological study in Mexico (Medina-Mora et al., 2007). Most participants were of an age typical for T2DM patients, were not regularly engaged in physical activity, and showed low adherence to dietary recommendations. This reflects common challenges in managing T2DM in clinical settings, consistent with other research in Mexican patients (Martínez Hernández et al., 2014).

The average HDRS score indicated mild to moderate DD symptoms across the sample. This finding mirrors the results of Martínez Hernández et al. (2014), which also found similar prevalences

using this scale in individuals at risk for T2DM (Martínez Hernández et al., 2014).

The internal consistency of the MMAS-8 was robust, confirming it as a reliable measure of medication adherence in Mexican patients with DD and T2DM. Inter-rater reliability for both the MMAS-8 and HDRS was excellent, indicating a high level of agreement between raters and ensuring that both scales can be reliably administered by different clinicians. This suggests that the Spanish version of the MMAS-8 accurately measures treatment adherence in individuals with T2DM.

Exploratory factor analysis of the MMAS-8 revealed three distinct factors: 'Low-Medium Adherence,' 'High Adherence,' and 'Specific Adherence Behaviors.' These factors accounted for a significant portion of the variance, with nearly a third of the variance associated with the first factor, which reflected low and medium adherence. Previous validation studies typically identify at least two factors in exploratory analyses (Zongo et al., 2016), and the identification of a third factor in this study may be explained by DD symptoms, such as anhedonia, which could influence factor loadings.

Confirmatory factor analysis supported the factor structure identified in the exploratory analysis, confirming the stability and reliability of the MMAS-8 in this population. This is consistent with prior validation research, which tends to find adequate fit results with the MMAS-8 (Martínez-Pérez et al., 2021).

Finally, the chi-square test revealed a statistically significant association between the severity of DD symptoms and T2DM medication adherence. Participants with higher symptom burdens were more likely to exhibit low adherence. As previously

Consistency, Reliability, and Validation of the 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Mexican Patients with Depressive Disorders and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

mentioned, research on Mexican patients at risk for T2DM has emphasized the importance of validating the MMAS-8 in this population (Martínez Hernández et al., 2014). This finding further supports the notion of a bidirectional relationship between DD and T2DM, where depressive symptoms exacerbate difficulties in managing chronic conditions like T2DM, ultimately leading to poorer health outcomes.

Limitations

This study had several limitations that should be acknowledged. The non-randomized, convenience sampling method may limit the generalizability of the findings, so caution is advised when applying these results to broader populations. Additionally, the cross-sectional design prevented the establishment of causal relationships. The absence of an assessment of cultural factors and stigma may have influenced participants' self-reporting of depressive symptoms and T2DM adherence behaviors.

Strengths

To the best of the research team's knowledge, it is the only study to evaluate the psychometric properties of the MMAS-8 in a Mexican population with both DD and T2DM. The rigorous methodological approach provided strong evidence supporting the scale's applicability in this population.

CONCLUSION

This Spanish version of the MMAS-8 offers healthcare providers a consistent, reliable, and valid tool for routinely assessing medication adherence in Mexican individuals with DD and T2DM. Furthermore, the significant association between the severity of DD symptoms and low

adherence highlights the importance of integrating mental health screening into the care of patients with T2DM.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Not applicable.

FUNDING

Not applicable.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors lack conflicts of interest to disclose.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, E., Lim, S., Lamptey, R., et al. (2022). Type 2 diabetes. *The Lancet*, 400(10365), 1803–1820. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(22\)01655-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(22)01655-5)
- American Diabetes Association Professional Practice Committee. (2022). 2. Classification and diagnosis of diabetes: Standards of medical care in diabetes—2022. *Diabetes Care*, 45 (Suppl. 1), S17–S38. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc22-S002>
- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM-5* (5th ed.). American Psychiatric Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425596>
- Cannon, A., Handelsman, Y., Heile, M., et al. (2018). Burden of illness in type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Journal of Managed Care & Specialty Pharmacy*, 24(9-a Suppl.), S5–S13. <https://doi.org/10.18553/jmcp.2018.24.9-a.s5>

Consistency, Reliability, and Validation of the 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Mexican Patients with Depressive Disorders and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

5. De Las Cuevas, C., & Peñate, W. (2015). Psychometric properties of the eight-item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8) in a psychiatric outpatient setting. *International Journal of Clinical and Health Psychology, 15*(2), 121–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijchp.2014.11.003>
6. Galicia-Garcia, U., Benito-Vicente, A., Jebbari, S., et al. (2020). Pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences, 21*(17), 6275. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21176275>
7. Gutiérrez-Rojas, L., Porras-Segovia, A., Dunne, H., et al. (2020). Prevalence and correlates of major depressive disorder: A systematic review. *Brazilian Journal of Psychiatry, 42*, 657–672. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1516-4446-2020-0650>
8. Hamilton, M. (1960). A rating scale for depression. *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery & Psychiatry, 23*(1), 56–62. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jnnp.23.1.56>
9. Holt, R. I., de Groot, M., & Golden, S. H. (2014). Diabetes and depression. *Current Diabetes Reports, 14*(6), 491. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11892-014-0491-3>
10. Horwitz, R. I., & Horwitz, S. M. (1993). Adherence to treatment and health outcomes. *Archives of Internal Medicine, 153*(16), 1863–1868. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archinte.1993.0410160017001>
11. Janežič, A., Locatelli, I., & Kos, M. (2017). Criterion validity of 8-item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in patients with asthma. *PLOS One, 12*(11), e0187835. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0187835>
12. Khan, M. A. B., Hashim, M. J., King, J. K., et al. (2020). Epidemiology of type 2 diabetes: Global burden of disease and forecasted trends. *Journal of Epidemiology and Global Health, 10*(1), 107–111. <https://doi.org/10.2991/jegh.k.191028.001>
13. Krass, I., Schieback, P., & Dhipayom, T. (2015). Adherence to diabetes medication: A systematic review. *Diabetic Medicine, 32*(6), 725–737. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dme.12651>
14. Martínez-Pérez, P., Orozco-Beltrán, D., Pómares-Gómez, F., et al. (2021). Validation and psychometric properties of the 8-item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8) in type 2 diabetes patients in Spain. *Atención Primaria, 53*(2), 101942. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aprim.2020.09.007>
15. Medina-Mora, M. E., Borges, G., Benjet, C., et al. (2007). Psychiatric disorders in Mexico: Lifetime prevalence in a nationally representative sample. *British Journal of Psychiatry, 190*, 521–528. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.bp.106.025841>
16. Moon, S. J., Lee, W. Y., Hwang, J. S., et al. (2017). Accuracy of a screening tool for medication adherence: A systematic review and meta-analysis of the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale-8. *PLOS One, 12*(11), e0187139. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0187139>
17. Otte, C., Gold, S. M., Penninx, B. W., et al. (2016). Major depressive disorder. *Nature Reviews Disease Primers, 2*(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrdp.2016.65>
18. Proudman, D., Greenberg, P., & Nellesen, D. (2021). The growing burden of major depressive disorders (MDD): Implications for researchers and policy makers. *Pharmacoeconomics, 39*, 619–625. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40273-021-01040-7>
19. R Core Team. (2023). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>
20. Roy, T., & Lloyd, C. E. (2012). Epidemiology of depression and diabetes: A systematic review. *Journal of Affective Disorders, 142*

Consistency, Reliability, and Validation of the 8-Item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Mexican Patients with Depressive Disorders and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

- (Suppl.), S8–S21. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0327\(12\)70004-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0327(12)70004-6)
21. Świątoniowska-Lonc, N., Tański, W., Polański, J., et al. (2021). Psychosocial determinants of treatment adherence in patients with type 2 diabetes: A review. *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity*, 14, 2701–2715. <https://doi.org/10.2147/DMSO.S308322>
 22. Trajković, G., Starčević, V., Latas, M., et al. (2011). Reliability of the Hamilton Rating Scale for Depression: A meta-analysis over a period of 49 years. *Psychiatry Research*, 189(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2010.12.007>
 23. Zongo, A., Guénette, L., Moisan, J., et al. (2016). Revisiting the internal consistency and factorial validity of the 8-item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale. *SAGE Open Medicine*, 4, 2050312116674850. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2050312116674850>